

is not necessary, since the same result is obtained whether there is any potassium chloride present or not.

In a stock containing Rubber 100, Zinc oxide 5, Stearic Acid 2, Sulfur 3, Accelerator 1, Antioxidant 1, the free sulfur value falls below 0.002 g. per one gram sample of the vulcanizate towards the end of vulcanization. Amperometric titration method will thus be more suitable for estimating such low concentrations of sulphur than the volumetric method of titration. We have actually found that the volumetric method gives reliable results upto about 0.005 g. of sulphur, below which the method is quite inapplicable as it becomes increasingly difficult to establish the endpoint. Moreover, the amperometric method is faster and does not require cooling of the reaction medium as is the case with the volumetric procedure². Further, the above results show that the presence of the different reagents added to the reaction medium for various purposes (such as for precipitating the accelerators which may be present in the rubber vulcanizates), does not interfere in the amperometric titration. Thus the amperometric method should be preferable for the estimation of free sulphur in rubber vulcanizates by the sulphite digestion procedure.

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Occurrence of Chemical Reaction in the Intermediate Zone during Electrolysis

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THE classical Hittorf mechanism clearly rules out any kind of change, not even a change of concentration in the intermediate zone during electrolysis. Though this is generally tacitly assumed to be true, we cite here some examples where such a tenet is clearly of no applicability.

Change of Concentration in the Intermediate Zone: This is best seen during electrolysis of a dichromate solution in a W-tube (Fig. 1). The tube is filled with a potassium dichromate solution ($N/20$ to $N/40$) and

a current of about 10 mA, is sent through the solution. In the course of about three hours a sharp boundary between a light coloured alkaline chromate solution and a deep coloured reddish brown chromic acid solution appears at B. Now if the current is still continued for overnight or so, another sharp boundary appears at B' and the portion BB' eventually becomes

Fig. 1

completely colourless and neutral. This is in clear violation of Hittorf principle as the current here brings about a fall in concentration in the intermediate zone in preference to the cathode zone (CB) and/or the anode zone (AB'). This happens with practically all electrolytes but is spectacularly shown by Cr(VI) and many dye solutions¹.

Chemical Reaction in the Intermediate Zone: That the intermediate zone can be a seat of reaction can be easily demonstrated by the experiment described below. The cell shown in Fig. 2 is filled with $N/1000$ solution of any electrolyte say, sodium chloride or sodium sulphate. The central limb M is filled with some benzene under nitrogen in which is dissolved a dye, say, chry-soidine. On sending a small current of say, 1 mA. through the two platinum foil electrodes it would be seen that the dye solution gets slowly decolorised, more than half being decolorised in a couple of days or so. Not only the dye gets decolorised but simultaneously the benzene layer becomes a strong seat of chemical reaction as seen by the fact that hydrogen and oxygen gets continuously liberated at the rate of about a ml per day in the intermediate zone M. These gases can be identified by withdrawal and analysis of the gas in M through the stopcock S from time to time. In any case some gas has to be let out

Fig. 2

periodically through S as otherwise the benzene will be pushed down too much into the horizontal portion and carried away in bulk. This discharge of colour and the liberation of hydrogen and oxygen clearly show that chemical reaction can take place in the intermediate zone during electrolysis.

Reaction in the intermediate zone is more strikingly shown if only benzene without any dye is used to start with and the electrolysis is continued for a long time. It would be observed in the course of a day or two of current conduction that benzene gets slowly reacted out to form a brown soluble substance which spreads out from the middle zone to the anode; this portion DBA then becomes progressively more brown as the current is continued, and a frothy deposit of an aromatic compound slowly gets formed near the top of the anolyte. If the electrolysis is continued for a week or two the whole solution in DBA extending from the bottom of the cathode limb right along the whole anode limb becomes deep brown in colour. Evidently, a slow but intense reaction goes on in the intermediate zone to produce a soluble substance from benzene. The substance formed can be easily isolated by evaporation to dryness and it appears to be a resinous polyphenol soluble in water. By using a slightly modified apparatus (a simple U-tube), similar resinous phenolic product is obtained from chlorobenzene and also from nitrobenzene, aniline etc. with rapid liberation of HCl in the case of C_6H_5Cl , HNO_2 in the case of $C_6H_5NO_2$, etc. These liquids being heavier than water are merely have to be left at the bottom as a small layer in the path of the current. It is evident that under the above condition the intermediate zone can by no means be considered a zone of no reactivity only offering passage to the migrating ions which carry the current; it is a seat of intense chemical activity even decomposing highly stable compounds such as chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, etc., particularly under conditions of anomalous electrolysis. It appears that this novel observation is somehow associated with non-Faradaic electrolysis reported by the author² and is probably due to electrical migration of active

free radicals which attack the benzene or chlorobenzene in the intermediate zone.

Further work is in progress and detailed results will be reported later. Thanks are due to Sri Prithwis Kumar Basu for essential experimental assistance.

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Spectrophotometric Studies on complex Formation of 5-Nitro-Salicylic Acid (5NSA) with Copper(II)

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC investigation showed the existence of two complexes between copper (II) and 5NSA. Application of Job, mole ratio and slope ratio methods indicated the formation of 1 : 1 complex at pH 4.0. The formation constant of this 1 : 1 complex has been determined employing Job, mole ratio and Foley and Anderson methods. Formation of 1 : 2 complex has also been indicated above pH 7.0. Its dissociation constant has been determined spectrophotometrically. The solution absorption spectra indicated a distorted octahedral structure for copper(II)-5-nitrosalicylate complexes.

As a part of a series of experiments on complex formation of 5-nitrosalicylic acid (5NSA) with various metal ions in solution¹⁻⁴, a spectrophotometric study of its reaction with copper(II) ions has been made. The results have been given below.